

**Politecnico
di Torino**

Cement-based composites containing functionalized carbon nanomaterials

Luca Lavagna^a, Daniel Suarez-Riera^b, Matteo Pavese^a

^a Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, C.so Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129, Torino, Italy

^b Department of Structural, Geotechnical and Building Engineering, Politecnico di Torino, C.so Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129 Torino, Italy

luca.lavagna@polito.it

Health monitoring of structures

Cement is used in many structures where crack propagation is extremely dangerous

Cement/concrete integrity must be monitored to avoid

Morandi bridge, 2018

Gulf of Mexico, 2010²

Carbon-based cement composites

Applications:

- Health on-line control for civil structures
- Experimental studies of a structure during dynamic loads (earthquakes)
- Stress sensors and structures on-line monitoring for oil&gas applications

Carbon-based cement composites

Improvement of: - Mechanical properties
- Electrical conductivity

FUNCTIONALIZATION NEEDED

Nanocomposites issues

BAD
dispersion in
water

BAD
dispersion in cement
due to agglomeration

BAD
interaction
with cement

Carbon materials are apolar, and in particular they tend to aggregate so it is difficult to disperse them in water

In order to achieve a good dispersion and interaction with the matrix it is necessary to attach polar groups on the surface

Dispersion/functionalization methods

Dispersion/functionalization methods

Preparation route

Chemical functionalization

TESTS

Cement + carbon fibers

Taguchi design of experiment

Test	Time [min]	Temperature [°C]	Acidic mixture	Flexural strength [MPa]
1	5	0	HNO ₃	12.6
2	5	30	1 HNO ₃ : 3 H ₂ SO ₄	12.6
3	5	60	3 H ₂ SO ₄ : 1 H ₂ O ₂	13.2
4	30	0	1 HNO ₃ : 3 H ₂ SO ₄	8.6
5	30	30	3 H ₂ SO ₄ : 1 H ₂ O ₂	10.5
6	30	60	HNO ₃	10.8
7	60	0	3 H ₂ SO ₄ : 1 H ₂ O ₂	12.2
8	60	30	HNO ₃	8.2
9	60	60	1 HNO ₃ : 3 H ₂ SO ₄	2.1

With factorial approach 27 tests

With Taguchi 9 tests

$$S/N = -10 * \log(\Sigma(1/Y^2)/n)$$

Time [min]	S/N [dB]	Temperature [°C]	S/N [dB]	Acidic mixture	S/N [dB]
5	22,1	0	20,5	HNO ₃	20,1
30	19,8	30	20,1	1 HNO ₃ : 3 H ₂ SO ₄	10,9
60	10,9	60	11,0	3 H ₂ SO ₄ : 1 H ₂ O ₂	21,4

Taguchi DOE results:

Flexural strength

Compressive strength

Taguchi DOE results:

Composites performance

Comparing samples with 0.1% reinforcement

Characterization of treated CFs

Comparing the **best** and the **worst** of Taguchi DOE

Thermogravimetric analysis

Raman

Cement + carbon nanotubes

Chemical functionalization

Experiment	Acid type	Time [min]	Temperature [°C]
A	Aqua Regia	30	30
B	Nitric	30	30
C	Piranha	30	30
D	Sulfonitric	30	30

Composites performance

Characterization of treated CNTs

Cement + Graphene Composites performance

Chemical functionalization

Acid	Time [min]
Sulfonitric	10
	20
	40
	60

Comparing samples with 0,1% by weight of cement

Characterization of treated CNTs

RAMAN

FE-SEM

A,B cement
C,D GNP 60'

Final remarks

Functionalization

- ✓ Key role of dispersion in water and in matrix
- ✓ Enhancement of composites mechanical properties
- ✓ Conductive cement

Thank you for your kind attention